

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Anonymization for Small Groups of Study Subjects

Use Case

Toni Lee is investigating how relatives of patients with a rare disease organize their everyday family life. To do so, Toni Lee is conducting long narrative interviews with the relatives in which they talk very personally about their family lives. The interviews also include sensitive topics such as limitations to their ability to work, unapproved medications, and euthanasia.

There are only around fifty people in Switzerland who suffer from this disease. Some of them know each other through self-help groups or encounters in waiting rooms. The doctors treating the patients also know them, of course. According to the open-research data requirements of the organization that financed the research project, Toni Lee must, if possible, publish the results of the project on a [repository](#).

The interviewees are signing an informed-consent document in which they agree that Toni Lee may use the interviews for the analysis and may publish them in an anonymized form in scientific publications.

What do you need to consider when anonymizing personal data for a small group of study subjects?

Anonymization is necessary to be able to use data in publications and presentations as well as to publish research data on anything like a repository. General guidelines on anonymization can be found [here](#).

In the case of a small group of study subjects, it is almost impossible to achieve complete anonymization, since conclusions can probably be drawn about a specific person purely on the basis of the group size, such as when a small group is characterized, as in the present case, by a specific characteristic (a rare disease but also a particular place of residence, a specific occupation, etc.) or when an individual can be identified through combining data.

What should you consider when publishing personal data from a small group of study participants, especially on a repository?

If data from a small group of study subjects cannot be sufficiently anonymized, then it is necessary to obtain informed consent from the study subjects to publish the data on a repository. The consent document for uploading data that cannot be sufficiently anonymized must refer to a specific [repository](#), even if the repository offers special security precautions like access controls or data-use agreements that make it possible to share personal data and other sensitive data. What the repository specifically offers in terms of security precautions and access controls should be checked in detail in advance.

In principle, the same applies to using research data in publications and presentations. Doing so is somewhat easier though, since usually one only needs to use or publish extracts from the datasets. This means that less information that can be related to a person is disclosed, so the risk of making individuals identifiable is lower. However, if complete anonymization is not possible, extracts from the datasets cannot be published either. It is always necessary to guarantee the protection of the study subjects. In particular, you must make sure that individuals cannot be identified through a combination of information from different publications (e.g., an interview passage in article A and an interview passage in article B).

What anonymization strategies can be used for small groups of study subjects?

In addition to deleting personal information and information that can be related to a specific person, the following anonymization methods may also be especially suited for small groups of study subjects:

- Generalize using classes or categories: Her husband worked as a municipal clerk. → Her husband worked in the civil service. / They live in Lenzburg. → They live in a small Swiss town.
- For particularly sensitive personal data that are difficult to anonymize, create an imaginary person with a mix of different characteristics from several people—or, conversely, turn one person into several people.
- Add red herrings by deliberately providing false information for characteristics that are not relevant to the analysis: The family lives in a house with several apartments on the outskirts of the city. → The family lives in a single-family house in the city center.

What does that mean for this case?

Toni Lee will not be able to publish the research data on a repository since consent has not been obtained for the publication of nonanonymized data and the data cannot be completely anonymized. The physicians treating the patients or other patients with the same rare disease would be able to identify individuals relatively easily based on the personal narratives.

Since informed consent was only obtained to use the research data in an anonymized form in publications, Toni Lee may not reproduce complete interviews or longer passages from them, since it is impossible to guarantee that they will be completely anonymous. To use shorter excerpts from the interviews, Toni Lee discusses the anonymization strategy with the interviewees, presents them with sensitive passages before publication, and asks them for their view on publishing the passage.

In the interest of scientific integrity, you must note in an appropriate place in the publication or presentation that the data have been anonymized and—provided that this does not compromise the protection of the study subjects—state how they have been anonymized.

Anonymization should be carried out or at least checked by the researchers themselves, as they know the research field well (better than a transcription company, for example) and are best able to assess the risks of reidentification. The study subjects must be informed that the data collected will be anonymized. In the interest of transparent scientific communication, it is also advisable to discuss the anonymization process with the study subjects and, if necessary, to provide them with the quotations from the interviews that will be used in a publication before it appears. It is also advisable to discuss the anonymization strategy with a data-protection officer.